

Supporting Information

Lignin-first fractionation of softwood lignocellulose using a mild dimethyl carbonate and ethylene glycol organosolv process

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1. Materials and methods

1.1. Chemicals and materials

Pine lignocellulose was purchased from Bemap Houtmeel B.V., cedar was obtained from a local wood shop (Dikhout, Groningen, the Netherlands), spruce was obtained from an Italian wood shop (Bricocenter), douglas fir was purchased from Hot Smocked (UK).

Solvents: tetrahydrofuran (THF), toluene, ethanol, dichloromethane (DCM), ethylacetate (EtOAc), acetone, and heptane were purchased from Macron Fine Chemicals. Dimethyl carbonate (99%, DMC), diethyl carbonate (DEC), ethylene glycol (EG, 99.5%), and 1,4-dioxane (99%) were purchased from Acros Organics. Monoglyme, tert-amyl alcohol, gamma-valero lactone (GVL), and normal-butanol were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Iron(III) triflate ($\text{Fe}(\text{OTf})_3$), bismuth triflate ($\text{Bi}(\text{OTf})_3$), *p*-toluenesulfonic acid were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Sulphuric acid (95-97%, H_2SO_4) was purchased from BOOM B.V. Octadecane (internal standard, 99%), N,O-Bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide, pyridine (99.8%), acetic anhydride, acetyl bromide, glacial acetic acid, *o*-toluidine, zinc dust, tetracosane, D-xylose, D-glucose, D-mannose, cellulose enzyme blend (CTec2) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Chloridric acid was purchased from BOOM B.V. All reagents were used as received.

1.2. Analytical procedures

Size exclusion chromatography analysis (SEC)

SEC analyses were performed using an Agilent HPLC 1100 system equipped with a refractive index detector. Three columns in series of MIXED type E (length 300 mm, i.d. 7.5 mm) were used. Polystyrene was used as a calibration standard (Agilent EasiCal PS-2 polystyrene kit, 500 - 20000 Da range). 0.02 g of the sample was dissolved in 3 mL of THF together with 15 μL of toluene as the flow marker and filtered (PTFE filter, pore size of 0.2 μm) prior to injection. The samples were fully soluble in THF. SEC analysis was intended with comparative purpose in order to understand the effectiveness of toluene extraction of Fraction 1 (Crude) resulting in Fraction 3 (toluene solubles) and Fraction 4 (toluene insolubles) in terms of relative molar masses.

High performance liquid chromatography analysis (HPLC) for sugars analysis

HPLC analysis was performed using an Agilent Technologies 1200 HPLC consisting of a Bio-Rad column HPX-87H and a refractive index detector. The mobile phase was a diluted sulfuric acid aqueous solution (5 mM) at a flow rate of 0.55 $\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and the column was kept at a temperature of 60 °C. HPLC analysis was used to determine glucose concentration and the combined concentration of xylose and mannose (since the two compounds gave overlapping peaks) according to the calibration.

High performance liquid chromatography analysis (HPLC) for lignin β -O-4' model compound study

HPLC analysis was performed using an Agilent Eclipse XDB-C18 5 Column (5 μm 4.6 x 150 mm). All samples were analyzed using a MeCN (0.1 vol % formic acid) (A)/H₂O(0.1 vol % formic acid) (B) gradient follow with a flow rate of 1.0 $\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. HPLC Method: 5% A/95% B for 10 minutes followed by gradient to 95% A/5% B over 30 minutes followed by 10 minutes at 95% A/5% B followed by a gradient to 5% A/95% B over 5 minutes followed by 5 minutes at 5% A/95% B a flow rate of 1.0 $\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. HPLC analysis was used to determine lignin model compound (MC), C2-acetal, guaiacol and EG-incorporated product according to the calibration versus 1,2,4,5 tetramethylbenzene which was used as internal standard. In the case of EG-incorporated product, the same response factor as for the starting material (MC) was used.

2D-NMR analysis

2D NMR analyses (HSQC and HMBC) were performed in CDCl_3 or $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{SO}$ using a Bruker Ascend 600 MHz spectrometer at RT.

1.3. Derivatization procedures

Lignin depolymerization products derivatization *via* silylation procedure

In a typical silylation procedure, 20 mg of products mixture from pinewood treatment were dissolved in 0.2 mL dry pyridine. After addition of 50 μL of N,O-Bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide, the mixture was stirred for 45 minutes at 50 °C and analyzed by Shimadzu GC-MS using a previously reported method with minor modifications.^[1] The GC apparatus was equipped with a HP5 column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm) and run with a temperature profile starting with a 2 min 60 °C isotherm followed by a 10 °C $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ ramp for 20 minutes to 280 °C, a temperature that was held for 13 minutes. All reagents were added under nitrogen flow. Standard settings: 1 μL injection, a split ratio of 20:1, a helium flow of 1 mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, injector and detector temperature 300 °C.

Aqueous phase (fraction 2) derivatization *via* acetylation procedure

Acetylation procedure was performed as follows: 0.5 mL of aqueous phase (fraction 2) was placed in a 20 mL pressure tube where 5 mL of acetic anhydride and 0.5 mL of pyridine were added. The mixture was incubated at 120 °C for 45 min. Then, 6 mL of water was added and extracted with 3 mL ethyl acetate and 3 mL DCM and the bottom layer was collected for GC-MS analysis. The GC apparatus was equipped with a HP5 column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm) and run with a temperature profile starting with a 14 °C $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ ramp from 100 °C to 300 °C, a temperature that was held for 5 minutes. Settings: 1 μL injection, a split ratio of 20:1, a helium flow of 0.96 mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, injector and detector temperature 300 °C.

1.4. Lignocellulose characterization

Water content determination (extractives at 105 °C)

Lignocellulose was placed in oven at 105 °C overnight; then cool down to RT in desiccator and water content was determined gravimetrically.

Toluene-ethanol extractives determination

Lignocellulose was put into a Soxhlet extraction apparatus. The sample was extracted with about 100 mL of 1:2 ethanol-toluene mixture (v/v) overnight. After this period, the solvent was evaporated in vacuo and extractives determined gravimetrically after constant weight was reached. Results are in accordance with the literature.^[2,3]

Lignin content determination

After extracting with toluene-ethanol mixture, lignocellulose was dried and used for lignin content determination according to NREL method (TP-510-42618).^[4] To the sample (50 mg) in a 20 mL MW vial 0.5 mL 72% H₂SO₄ was added. The mixture was manually stirred with a glass rod for 1 h at 30 °C (every 5 to 10 minutes). Then, 14 mL of deionized water was added in order to reach 3% H₂SO₄ and the mixture was refluxed for 4 hours. The mixture was filtered and an aliquot of the filtrate was taken for acid soluble lignin (ASL) determination measuring UV absorption at 240 nm (absorptivity at 240 nm: 12 L $\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$). Then, the solid was washed with 200 mL of deionized water and the filter was dried until constant weight for acid insoluble lignin (AIL) determination. Lignin content determination was conducted in duplicate. Total lignin content was calculated as AIL+ASL. Results are in accordance with the literature.^[2,3]

Derivatization Followed by Reductive Cleavage (DFRC) procedure for monomers theoretical yield and β -O-4' content determination

After extracting with toluene-ethanol mixture, lignocellulose was dried and sieved (particles size: between 500 and 200 μm) and used for β -O-4' content determination and calculation of theoretical monomer yield and following DFRC reported procedure.^[5] To a 10 mL round bottom flask with around 20 mg of wood cell

material 3 mL of acetyl bromide solution was added (20/80 AcBr/Acetic acid v/v). The mixture was stirred at 130 rpm, 50 °C for 3 hours. Then, the solvent was completely removed by rotary evaporation below 50 °C (bath temperature). The residue was dissolved in 3 mL of stock solution (5/4/1 dioxane/acetic acid/ water v/v/v). Zinc dust (50 mg) was added to a well-stirred solution and stirred for 60 minutes. Then, the mixture was quantitatively transferred to a separating funnel with DCM (10 mL) and saturated NH₄Cl (10 mL) and IS (tetracosane, 0.2 mg; 0.1 mL of a solution 2 mg·mL⁻¹) were added. The pH of aqueous phase was adjusted to less than 3 by adding 3% HCl aqueous solution. The water phase was extracted with 5 mL DCM. The combined DCM fractions were dried over MgSO₄ and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in 1.1 mL DCM and then 0.4 mL stock solution (1/1 dry pyridine/acetic anhydride v/v) was added under nitrogen. The solution was vortexed and stirred for 1 h. All volatiles were co-evaporated with EtOH (twice) and the residue was dissolved in 0.5 mL DCM for GC-FID analysis. Theoretical monomer yield was calculated using response factors and retention time from literature using an internal standard (tetracosane). The liquid phase was analysed by a Shimadzu GC-2014 equipped with a FID detector using helium as a carrier gas. Standard settings: 2 µL injection, a split ratio of 30:1, a helium flow of 1 mL·min⁻¹. The GC apparatus was equipped with a HP5 column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm) and run with a temperature profile starting with a 1 min 140 °C isotherm followed by a 3 °C·min⁻¹ ramp to 240 °C (hold time: 1 min). Then, the temperature was raised to 300 with a 30 °C·min⁻¹ ramp and 12 minutes hold time. GC injector temperature: 220 °C, detector: 300 °C.

The calculations were done as following.

	G _{cis}	G _{trans}
Relative retention time	0.59	0.68
Response factor	1.85	1.85

$$m_{Gc \text{ or } Gt} = \text{response factor} \times \frac{\text{Area}_{Gc \text{ or } Gt}}{\text{Area}_{IS}} \times m_{IS} \quad (\text{eq. S1})$$

$$\text{mol}_{Gc+Gt} = \frac{m_{Gc}+m_{Gt}}{264.277} \quad (\text{eq. S2})$$

$$\text{Theoretical monomer yield } (\text{mol}_{Gc+Gt} \cdot m_{lignin}^{-1})[E] = \frac{\text{mol}_{Gc+Gt}}{m_{lignin}} \quad (\text{eq. S3})$$

$$\text{Depolymerization efficiency } [DE] = \left[\left(\frac{\text{mol}_{C2-acetal}}{m_{lignin}} \right) / E \right] \times 100 \quad (\text{eq. S4})$$

$$\text{Monomers yield } (\text{mol}_{Gc+Gt} \cdot \text{mol}_{lignin}^{-1})[Y] = \frac{\text{mol}_{Gc+Gt}}{\text{mol}_{lignin}} \quad (\text{eq. S5})$$

$$\text{mol}_{lignin} = \frac{m_{lignin}}{MW_A} \quad (\text{eq. S6})$$

MW_A=196,202 g/mol, being A

$$\text{Frequency } \beta - O - 4' \text{ moiety } (\%) = \sqrt{(Y/100)} \times 100 \quad (\text{eq. S7})$$

Figure S1. GC-FID chromatogram of DFRC monomers from pinewood.

Carbohydrates determination

Extractives free lignocellulose was dried and sieved (particles size: between 500 and 200 μm) and used for sugars determination according to a modified procedure of NREL TP-510-42618.^[4] Sample (40 mg) was placed in a pressure tube together with 72 wt% aqueous sulfuric acid (0.4 mL). The mixture was manually stirred with a glass rod for 1 h at 30 °C (every 5 to 10 minutes). Water (11.2 mL) was added and the tube was sealed. In parallel, a control reaction was performed in order to estimate the decomposition of carbohydrates during analysis process. D-xylose (5 mg), D-glucose (20 mg), and D-mannose (10 mg) were dissolved in 3 wt% aqueous sulfuric acid (11.6 mL). All the samples were incubated at 120 °C for 1 h. After cooling in ice bath a sample was taken and subjected to HPLC analysis.

1.5. Pulp characterization

Lignin content, degree of delignification (DD), solid residue yield and solid residue purity determination

AIL and ASL were determined as previously described for feedstock characterization. Degree of delignification (**DD**) was calculated as follows:

$$m_{AIL+ASL \text{ in pulp}} = m_{pulp} \times W_{AIL+ASL \text{ in pulp}} \quad (\text{eq. S8})$$

$$DD = \frac{m_{AIL+ASL \text{ in wood}} - m_{AIL+ASL \text{ in pulp}}}{m_{AIL+ASL \text{ in wood}}} \quad (\text{eq. S9})$$

$$m_{AIL+ASL \text{ in wood}} = m_{wood} \times W_{AIL+ASL \text{ in wood}} \times W_{extractives \text{ at } 105^\circ\text{C}} \quad (\text{eq. S10})$$

$$\text{solid residue yield} = \frac{m_{solid \text{ residue}}}{m_{wood}} \times 100 \quad (\text{eq. S11})$$

$$\text{solid residue purity} = 100 - (AIL_{\% \text{ in solid residue}} + ASL_{\% \text{ in solid residue}}) \quad (\text{eq. S12})$$

Carbohydrates determination

Carbohydrates content determination was performed as previously reported for lignocellulose characterization.

1.6. Enzymatic digestion of pulp

Glucose calibration

A calibration curve for the photometric studies was obtained as following: 20 μL of standard solutions of glucose in water ($0.9\text{--}10\text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) were added to 20 mL microwave vials containing 3 mL of 6 wt% solution of *o*-toluidine in glacial acetic acid (1.26 mL *o*-toluidine in 18.8 mL glacial acetic acid). The obtained mixtures were heated to 100 °C for 10 minutes and their absorbance was measured at 630 nm versus a blank sample. Each measurement was triplicated.

Measurement of enzymatic activity

The activity of Cellic CTec2 enzyme used for hydrolysis of pulp was determined using a standard procedure from NREL (NREL/TP-510-42628)^[6]. 1 FPU stands for enzyme activity where 2 mg (4%) glucose are released from 50 mg of filter #1 paper (Whatman, 1cm x 6 cm) in 1.5 mL of citrate buffer (pH = 4.8) at 50 °C in 60 min. To 5 glass vials, filter #1 paper (50 mg), 1.5 mL of citrate buffer, 20 microL of a 3,5%wt sodium azide (to prevent the growth of microorganisms) in water and Ctec2 solution (1 μL , 5 μL , 10 μL , 20 μL , 50 μL) were added. The vials were heated at 50 °C in heating block for 60 minutes. After cooling down in ice-bath, 40 μL samples were taken and added to 20 mL microwave vials containing 3 mL of a solution 6 wt% of *o*-toluidine in glacial acetic acid. The obtained mixtures were heated to 100 °C for 10 minutes and their absorbance was measured at 630 nm versus a blank sample. Each measurement was triplicated. 10 μL of CTec2 solution was found to be an appropriate amount and glucose concentration obtained from the absorption value was used to calculate the activity of enzyme in filter paper units (FPU): 130 FPU $\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of the pulp

When dry pulp was used the biomass recovered after reaction was washed extensively with acetone (about 20 mL) and air dried. When fresh, biomass was washed extensively first with acetone (about 20 mL) and then water (about 20 mL) and grounded. After determination of the dry weight, the pulp corresponding to 45 mg of dry-weight solid was placed in a glass vial together with 20 μL of a 3.5 wt% sodium azide and 1.5 mL of citrate buffer (pH=5) containing enzyme (25 or 50 FPU per gram of dry weight pulp). The vials were stirred at 50 rpm and kept at 50 °C. Samples were taken after 1, 24, 48 and 72 hours and glucose concentration was determined using spectrophotometry as described above. Experiments with fresh pulp were conducted in duplicate. For the experiments with hydrolyzed pulp 0.8 g of wet pulp was treated in 5 mL of aqueous sulfuric acid (5 wt% H_2SO_4) for 1h at 120 °C.

1.7. Test reactions with xylose, mannose and glucose

Typically, 1 mmol of substrate (D-(+)-xylose, D-(+)-mannose or D-(+)-glucose) was reacted with 10 equivalents of EG and 1 mol % H₂SO₄ in 3 ml DMC for 20 minutes at 140 °C. Then, 2 mL of a water solution (buffer K₂HPO₄/KH₂PO₄ pH=8) was added to the DMC phase in order to neutralize the reaction mixture followed by 1 mL of DCM in order to improve the separation. Then, the mixture was vortexed and the organic phase was separated. The aqueous phase was extracted with DCM (2 mL x 2). The aqueous phase was used for characterization after removing water by rotary evaporation. A blank reaction of D-(+)-glucose in DMC/ H₂SO₄ without EG was performed under the same conditions and treated in the same way.

1.8. Test reactions with lignin model compound (MC) with increasing EG amount

Phenolic β-O-4' lignin model compound (MC) was prepared as previously reported.^[7] Substrate (MC, 50 mg, 0.15608 mmol), and ethylene glycol (4, 8, 16 or 32 equivalents) was placed in a 20 mL microwave vial and a magnetic stirring bar added. Internal standard (1,2,4,5-tetramethylbenzene, 3.0 mL of a 0.1 mmol·mL⁻¹ stock solution in DMC) was added. Solvent (DMC), sufficient to make the final reaction volume up to 6 mL was added and the vial was sealed. The solution was stirred and heated to 140 °C in an oil bath. An initial time point sample was taken immediately prior to catalyst addition. The catalyst, H₂SO₄, (e.g. 2 mol%, from a stock solution in DMC) was added by syringe with a thin needle through the septum of the microwave vial. Samples (100 μL) were taken from the vial through the septum with a thin needle at intervals over a 6 hour period and quenched onto HPLC sample vials containing 900 μL of a 60:40 MeCN:H₂O solution basified with Et₃N. The samples were then analyzed by HPLC.

2. β-O-4' cleavage mechanism under acidic conditions

Figure S2. β-O-4' lignin motif cleavage under acidolysis conditions, in conjunction with stabilization of reactive intermediates: C2 and C3 pathway

3. Lignocellulose composition and β -O-4' content

Lignocellulose	Water content (extractives at 105 °C)	Extractives (Toluene/Ethanol mixture)	AIL (wt %)	ASL (wt %)	Lignin (wt %)	β -O-4' content ^[a]	Theoretical monomer yield (mol/g _{lignin})
Pinewood	6.8	2.3	25.8	1.6	27.4	28.9	4.27*10 ⁻⁴
Cedar	6.6	7.8	33.5	3.0	36.5	26.5	3.64*10 ⁻⁴
Spruce	5.5	1.5	27.4	2.8	30.2	28.5	4.14*10 ⁻⁴
Douglas Fir	4.0	5.0	30.3	2.5	32.8	27.0	3.71*10 ⁻⁴

Table S1. Lignocellulose characterization. [a] Results are in accordance with literature^[8]

Lignocellulose	Cellulose (wt %)	Hemicellulose (wt %)	Lignin (wt %)
Pinewood	43.7	17.2	27.4

Table S2. Composition of pine lignocellulose

4. Model compound study in the presence of increasing EG

Figure S3. β -O-4' model compound (MC) reaction to EG-incorporated product (X), guaiacol (G) and C2-acetal

Figure S4. Time course analysis for the reaction of the Phenolic β -O-4' model compound (MC) with 2 mol% H₂SO₄, 4 eq. Ethylene Glycol in DMC at 140 °C.

Figure S5. Time course analysis for the reaction of the Phenolic β -O-4' model compound (MC) with 2 mol% H₂SO₄, 8 eq. Ethylene Glycol in DMC at 140 °C.

Figure S6. Time course analysis for the reaction of the Phenolic β -O-4' model compound (MC) with 2 mol% H₂SO₄, 16 eq. Ethylene Glycol in DMC at 140 °C.

Figure S7. Time course analysis for the reaction of the Phenolic β -O-4' model compound (MC) with 2 mol% H₂SO₄, 32 eq. Ethylene Glycol in DMC at 140 °C.

5. Solvents screening

Entry	Solvent	Yield C2-acetal [wt% to AIL+ASL]	δ [MPa ^{0.5}]	EG + solvents δ [MPa ^{0.5}]	ϵ_r
1	1,4-Dioxane	5.7	20.5	20.8	2.21
2	Dimethoxyethane (Monoglyme)	6.1	17.6	18.0	7.3
3	Toluene	5.3	18.2	18.5	2.38
4	Acetone	4.3	20.3	20.6	21.01
5	<i>t</i> -Amyl alcohol	1.1	20.5	20.8	5.81
6	<i>n</i> -Butanol	0.0	23.3	23.5	17.8
7	Dimethyl carbonate (DMC)	8.0	20.3	20.6	3.1
8	Diethyl carbonate (DEC)	8.0	18.0	18.4	2.83
9	Heptane	2.0	15.3	15.7	1.92
10	GVL	2.8	23.1	23.3	36.5

Table S3. Solvents parameters^[9] and C2-acetal yield. Reaction conditions: 1.5 g pine, 0.9 mL EG (66 wt% to pine), total volume 30 mL, 140 °C, time: 30 min (+10 min from 25 °C to 140 °C), 0.15 mmol H₂SO₄ (1 wt % to pinewood). δ = Hildebrand solubility parameter, ϵ_r = dielectric constant. EG δ = 29.9 MPa^{0.5}.

6. Optimization of reaction conditions

Entry	EG [wt % to pinewood]	C2-acetal yield [wt % to ASL+AIL]	Degree of delignification [%]	EG + DMC δ [MPa ^{0.5}]	Solid residue yield (wt%)	Solid residue purity (wt%) ^[b]
1	66	8.7	33.9	20.6	56.8	69.7
2	170	8.9	34.6	21.0	59.3	71.3
3	220	8.3	41.8	21.3	58.2	73.4
4	300	8.9	56.1	21.6	59.6	80.8
5	400 ^[a]	8.8±0.1	77.3	22.0	44.2	86.6
6	500	6.9	66.6	22.5	47.8	81.8
7	590	7.3	78.7	22.9	45.1	87.7
8	2220 (pure EG)	1.1	62.5	29.9	65.1	85.0

Table S4. EG effect on C2-acetal yield, degree of delignification (DD) and solvent mixture Hildebrand solubility parameter (δ). Reaction conditions: 1.5 g pine, 0.9 mL EG (XX wt % to pine), total volume 30 mL, 140 °C, time: 30 min (+10 min from 25 °C to 140 °C), 0.3 mmol H₂SO₄ (2 wt % to pinewood).[a] the reaction was repeated twice and G-C2-acetal yield was found 8.8±0.1; [b] based on ASL+AIL

Figure S8. Ethylene glycol amount influence on C2-acetal yield using 0.15 or 0.3 mol catalyst. Reaction conditions: 1.5 g pine, EG (indicated amount), solvent: DMC, total volume 30 mL, 140 °C, time: 30 minutes (+10 min from 25 °C to 140 °C), catalyst: H₂SO₄

Figure S9. Time influence on C2-acetal yield. Reaction conditions: 1.5 g pine, 400 wt % EG to pinewood, solvent: DMC, total volume 30 mL, temperature: 140 °C, catalyst: 2 wt % to pinewood H₂SO₄

Figure S10. Temperature influence on C2-acetal yield. Reaction conditions: 1.5 g pine, 400 wt % EG to pinewood, solvent: DMC, total volume 30 mL, 30 min, catalyst: 2 wt % to pinewood H₂SO₄

7. Pinewood fractionation

7.1. Fraction 1. Organic phase (crude)

Figure S11. GC-MS analysis of Fraction 1 before (black) and after silylation (pink)

Figure S12. HSQC NMR of fraction 1 in d_6 -DMSO

Figure S13. HSQC and HMBC NMR of fraction 1 in d_6 -DMSO (HSQC: green [-CH/-CH₃]/pink [-CH₂]; HMBC: brown)

Figure S14. Reference HSQC and HMBC NMR of C2-acetal in d_6 -DMSO (HSQC blue: -CH₂, red: -CH/-CH₃, HMBC: green)

Figure S15. SEC analysis of crude (solid red line), toluene soluble (dashed green line) and toluene insoluble (dot black line) fractions.

7.2. Fraction 4. Toluene insoluble fraction

Figure S16. GC-MS analysis of toluene insoluble fraction (Fraction 4) after silylation

Figure S17. HSQC NMR of fraction 4 (brown/blue) overlapped with C2-acetal reference (purple/green)

7.3. Fraction 3. Toluene soluble fraction

Figure S18. GC-MS analysis: toluene soluble fraction after silylation

7.3.1. Hibbert ketone region:

Figure S19. Hibbert ketone formation from β -O-4' lignin motif

Figure S20. GC-MS analysis, Hibbert ketone derivatives region

Proposed structure for m/z 294 (HK1, HK2)

HB1-TMS can originate from Hibbert's ketone **HK1** through Lobry de Bruyn–van Ekenstein transformation^[10]; **HB2-TMS** can originate from Hibbert's ketone and EG as previously reported^{[11],[12]}

HK1 (r.t. 17,06 min)

HK2 (r.t. 17,33 min)

Proposed structures for m/z=384 (HK3, HK4, HK5)

HB3-TMS, HB4-TMS and HB5-TMS can originate from β -O-4' linkage cleavage *via* C3 pathway (Figure S19).^{[11],[12],[13],[14]}

HK3 (r.t. 18,45 min)

HK4 (r.t. 18,58 min)

HK5 (r.t. 19,23 min)

7.3.2. Dimers region:

Figure S21. GC-MS analysis (dimer region).

Proposed structure for m/z 416 (D1,D3)

Possible reaction pathway for **P1** originating from β -1 units in lignin:

2 isomers possible, from β -1 subunit of lignin, matching quite good with fragmentation of not-silylated one.^[15]

D1 (r.t. 21,9 min):

D3 (r.t. 24,78 min)

Proposed structures for m/z 502 (D4,D9)

From β -O-4/ β -5:C2/C2 pathway (**Figure 6**) as previously reported^[13,15,16]

From β - β linkages, as previously reported^[13,15,16]

P4 is not reported but it would originate from C2-aldehyde in case of aldol condensation reaction instead of EG-stabilization

D4 (r.t. 25,35 min)

D9 (r.t. 30,44 min)

Proposed structure for m/z 562 (D6)

P5

P4 is not reported but it would originate for condensation of 2 G-acetal molecules.

D6 (r.t. 27,46 min)

Proposed structure for m/z 500 (D8)

P6

Not reported but it would originate from cleaving a unit with B-O-4/B-5:C3/C3 pathway (Figure 6)

D8 (r.t. 29,59 min)

Hypotheses for m/z=442 (D10)

From β -O-4/B-5:C2/C3 pathway (**Figure 6**) as previously reported [13,15,16]

D10 (r.t. 31,51)

Fragmentations of D2, D5, D7

D2 (r.t. 22,38 min)

D5 (r.t. 26,23 min)

D7 (r.t. 27,53 min)

Figure S22. HSQC NMR of *Fraction 3*

Figure S23. HSQC and HMBC NMR of **Fraction 3** in d_6 -DMSO (HSQC: brown [-CH/-CH₃]/blue [-CH₂]; HMBC: green)

7.4. Fraction 2. Aqueous phase

Figure S24. GPC analysis of Fraction 2

Figure S25. HSQC NMR of Fraction 2 in d_6 -DMSO (blue: $-CH_2$, red: $-CH/-CH_3$)

Glucose (DMC/EG/ H_2SO_4):

Figure S26. Reaction conditions: D-(+)-glucose (1mmol), solvent: DMC (3 mL), EG (10 eq), H_2SO_4 (1mol %), 140 °C, 20 minutes

Figure S27. HSQC (red $-CH$ and $-CH_3$, blue $-CH_2$) and HMBC (green) NMR of water phase of reaction displayed in Fig. S26

Figure S28. HSQC NMR of Fraction 2 (grey) and water phase of reaction displayed in Fig. S26 (red: $-CH$ and $-CH_3$, blue $-CH_2$)

Glucose (DMC/H₂SO₄):

Figure S29. Reaction conditions: D-(+)-glucose (1mmol), solvent: DMC (3 mL), H₂SO₄ (1mol %), 140 °C, 20 minutes

Figure S30. HSQC NMR of native glucose (grey) and water phase of reaction displayed in Fig. S29 (red: -CH and -CH₃, blue -CH₂)

Xylose (DMC/EG/H₂SO₄):

Figure S31. Reaction conditions: D-(+)-xylose (1mmol), solvent: DMC (3 mL), EG (10 eq), H₂SO₄ (1mol %), 140 °C, 20 minutes

Figure S32. HSQC (red $-CH$ and $-CH_3$, blue $-CH_2$) and HMBC (green) NMR of water phase of reaction displayed in Fig. S31

Figure S33. HSQC NMR of Fraction 2 (grey) and water phase of reaction displayed in Fig. S31 (red: $-CH$ and $-CH_3$, blue $-CH_2$)

Mannose (DMC/EG/H₂SO₄):

Figure S34. Reaction conditions: D-(+)-mannose (1mmol), solvent: DMC (3 mL), EG (10 eq), H₂SO₄ (1mol %), 140 °C, 20 minutes

Figure S35. HSQC (red -CH and -CH₃, blue -CH₂) and HMBC (green) NMR of water phase of reaction displayed in Fig. S34

Figure S36. HSQC NMR of fraction 2 (grey) and water phase of reaction displayed in **Fig. S34** (red: -CH and -CH₃, blue -CH₂).

Figure S37. GC-MS analysis of *Fraction 2* after derivatization *via* acetylation procedure.

8. Pulp characterization

Entry	EG (% wt to pinewood) (mL)	AIL (wt %)	ASL (wt %)	Cellulose (%)	Hemicellulose (%)	EG (wt %)	EG loss compared to initial EG (%)
1	0 (0.0)	49.0	1.9	39.4	0.2	0	0
2	66 (0.9)	28.1	2.2	54.9	6.0	0.130	6,9
3	300 (3.8)	17.6	1.6	58.1	9.2	0.146	1,9
4	400 (5.4)	12.0	1.4	65.8	7.9	0.154	1,1

Table S5. Composition of residual pulp from experiments with different amount of EG (0-400wt % to pinewood)

9. Enzymatic digestion of the pulp

Glucose determination and enzymatic digestion were performed following reported procedure.^[17]

Figure S38. Enzymatic digestion of dry pulps treated with different amount of EG (0, 66, 300 and 400wt % to pinewood). 25 FPU/g of dry pulp were used.

Figure S39. Enzymatic digestion of fresh not hydrolysed pulp (25 and 50 FPU/g dry pulp) and hydrolysed pulp (50 FPU/g dry pulp)

10. Degree of delignification (DD) and depolymerization efficiency (DE) in reductive catalytic fractionation of softwood

Entry	Lignocellulose	Monomers yield (wt%)	Monomers selectivity (%)	DD (%)	DE (%)	ref
1	Pinewood	22	4- <i>n</i> -propyl guaiacol (7.2); dihydroconiferyl alcohol (92.8)	79 ^[a]	n.d.	[18]
2	Pinewood	23	2-methoxy-4-(prop-1-enyl)phenol (100)	54 ^[a]	92	[19]
3	Pinewood	9	2-methoxy-4-propylphenol (86); 2-methoxy-4-(propenyl)- phenols (14)	84	75	[8]
4	Spruce	12	2-methoxy-4-propylphenol (91); 2-methoxy-4-(propenyl)- phenols (9)	84	93	[8]

Table S6. Monomers yield and selectivity in reductive catalytic fractionation. [a] Based on lignin oil yield to initial lignin content

11. EG mass balance at optimized conditions

Entry	Fraction	EG in each fraction (g)	EG in each fraction (%)
1	Initial EG	5.99	-
2	EG in solid residue	0.06	1.1
3	EG in G-C2-acetal	0.01	0.2
4	EG in ethylene carbonate	0.39	6.6
5	EG in Fraction 2 (unreacted in aqueous phase)	3.14	52.4
6	SUM		60.2

Table S7. EG mass balance at optimized reaction conditions (1.5 g pine, 5.4 mL, 24.6 mL DMC, 140 °C 30 min, catalyst: 2 wt % to pinewood H₂SO₄)

12. References

- [1] M. R. Kornreich, P. Issenberg, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **1972**, *20*, 1109–1113.
- [2] M. D’Auria, M. Mecca, L. Todaro, *J. Wood Chem. Technol.* **2017**, *37*, 163–170.
- [3] H. Wang, R. Srinivasan, F. Yu, P. Steele, Q. Li, B. Mitchell, *Energy and Fuels* **2011**, *25*, 3758–3764.
- [4] A. Sluiter, B. Hames, R. Ruiz, C. Scarlata, J. Sluiter, D. Templeton, D. Crocker, *NREL TP-510-42618* **2012**, 1–3.
- [5] F. Lu, J. Ralph, *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **1997**, *45*, 4655–4660.
- [6] B. Adney, J. Baker, *NREL TP-510-42628* **2008**, 1–8.
- [7] C. W. Lahive, P. J. Deuss, C. S. Lancefield, Z. Sun, D. B. Cordes, C. M. Young, F. Tran, A. M. Z. Slawin, J. G. De Vries, P. C. J. Kamer, et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 8900–8911.
- [8] M. V. Galkin, A. T. Smit, E. Subbotina, K. A. Artemenko, J. Bergquist, W. J. J. Huijgen, J. S. M. Samec, *ChemSusChem* **2016**, *9*, 3280–3287.
- [9] a) W. Zeng, Y. Du, Y. Xue, H. L. Frisch, in *Physical Properties of Polymers Handbook* (Ed: J. E. Mark), Springer, New York, **2007**, p. 289; b) X. Gui, Z. Tang and W. Fei, *Measurement and prediction of the solubility of CO₂ in ester mixture, Low Carbon Economy* **2**, **2011**, pp. 26–31; c) C. Reichardt, T. Welton, *Solvents and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry*, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, **2010**, pp. 65–106; d) J. Durkee, *Cleaning with Solvents: Science and Technology*, William Andrew: Norwich, NJ, **2013**, p. 538; e) D. R. Lide, *CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, 87th edn*, Boca Raton, USA: CRC Press, **2006**, section 6, p 135; f) *Vogel's Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry (5th Ed.)*, Revised by Brian S. Furniss, Antony J. Hannaford, Peter W. G. Smith, and Austin R. Tatchell, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1514 pp; g) C. Wohlfarth, in *Static Dielectric Constants of Pure Liquids and Binary Liquid Mixtures* (Ed: M. D. Lechner), Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, **2015**, pp. 96–96. [10] Z. Wang, S. Qiu, K. Hirth, J. Cheng, J. Wen, N. Li, Y. Fang, X. Pan, J. Y. Zhu, *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2019**, *7*, 10808–10820.
- [11] D. M. Miles-Barrett, A. R. Neal, C. Hand, J. R. D. Montgomery, I. Panovic, O. S. Ojo, C. S. Lancefield, D. B. Cordes, A. M. Z. Slawin, T. Lebl, et al., *Org. Biomol. Chem.* **2016**, *14*, 10023–10030.
- [12] J. R. D. Montgomery, K. Kempf, D. M. Miles-Barrett, O. Kempf, T. Lebl, N. J. Westwood, *ChemSusChem* **2019**, *12*, 190–193.
- [13] P. J. Deuss, M. Scott, F. Tran, N. J. Westwood, J. G. De Vries, K. Barta, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2015**, *137*, 7456–7467.
- [14] C. S. Lancefield, P. C. J. Kamer, K. Barta, J. G. de Vries, N. J. Westwood, P. J. Deuss, C. W. Lahive, *ChemSusChem* **2016**, *9*, 2974–2981.

- [15] P. J. Deuss, C. S. Lancefield, A. Narani, J. G. de Vries, N. J. Westwood, K. Barta, T. D. Foust, G. T. Beckham, Á. T. Martinez, J. C. del Rio, et al., *Green Chem.* **2017**, *19*, 2774–2782.
- [16] C. W. Lahive, P. J. Deuss, C. S. Lancefield, Z. Sun, D. B. Cordes, C. M. Young, F. Tran, A. M. Z. Slawin, J. G. De Vries, P. C. J. Kamer, et al., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 8900–8911.
- [17] I. Kumaniaev, E. Subbotina, J. Sävmarker, M. Larhed, M. V. Galkin, J. S. M. Samec, *Green Chem.* **2017**, *19*, 5767–5771.
- [18] K. M. Torr, D. J. van de Pas, E. Cazeils, I. D. Suckling, *Bioresour. Technol.* **2011**, *102*, 7608–7611.
- [19] M. V. Galkin, J. S. M. Samec, *ChemSusChem* **2014**, *7*, 2154–2158.